

GREAT EASTERN THINKERS ABOUT MATHEMATICS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012470>

Dekhkambayeva Zulfiya Abubakirovna

Associate Professor of the Department "Methodology of Preschool Education" of the Tashkent State University named after Nizami, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences

Golovchenko Irina Nikolaevna

Student of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Ключевые слова: *формирования, история, математика, методы, восточные, мыслители*

Key words.

formations, history, mathematics, methods, Eastern, thinkers

One of the main principles of didactic theories is that when teaching any subject, it is necessary to pay attention to the history of the emergence and development of this scientific discipline. Therefore, when teaching mathematics in schools, along with the basic theories, methods, formulas and their stages of development, it is of great importance to use information about scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of mathematical science.

It is known that students' interest in acquiring knowledge increases several times, their activity in mastering the material increases in the aggregate presentation of historical information with basic mathematical materials. This is also confirmed by the fact that the discovery of the depths of the studied material in conjunction with the scientific work of an individual scientist and historical aspect is of particular interest to students. Today, there are very few methodological recommendations on the use of historical materials in the process of teaching mathematics. It is believed that when teaching mathematics in the schools of our republic, it is necessary for students to be widely acquainted with the biographies of mathematicians from Central Asia. The rapid development of scientific achievements in the last years of the twentieth century was the result of scientific research and discoveries in past centuries. Today's high level of mathematical science is based on detailed studies of the past.

The achievements of mathematics in the Middle and Near East, and in particular in Central Asia, have left a significant mark on the development of world mathematical science. The great natives of Central Asia - al-Kashi, al-Fergani, Omar

Khayyam, al-Khwarizmi and many others wrote brilliant pages in the history of mathematics. Their works not only preserved and generalized the mathematical legacy of previous periods, but also developed fundamentally new methods and laid the foundation for new branches of science. A very important place in the work of Eastern mathematicians was occupied by: compiling trigonometric tables, solving a number of important arithmetic problems (spreading the decimal positional number system using zero, creating an absolute sexagesimal positional number system, methods for extracting roots with any natural indicator), and also a great role in the creation of algebra as an independent science.

Al-Khwarizmi is the author of works on arithmetic and algebra, which played an enormous role in the history of world mathematics. The goal set in al-Khwarizmi's treatise on arithmetic is to present and explain the Indian decimal positional number system and to identify its advantages over other number systems. After explaining the basic principles of the new system, al-Khwarizmi proceeds to a detailed presentation of the rules for representing numbers, and then to the basic operations with integers and fractions, and, finally, to the method of extracting square roots. The influence of al-Khwarizmi's arithmetical work on the further development of mathematics in the countries of the East, and then in Europe, is very great: he initiated the widespread use of the decimal positional number system using zero.

The second mathematical work of al-Khwarizmi "Algebra" or "A short book on the calculation of algebra and al-muqabala" laid the foundation for the independent development of algebra. In fact, "Algebra" of al-Khwarizmi is considered as the foundation and cornerstone of this science. The name of the modern science algebra bears the imprint of the influence of the work of al-Khwarizmi: the word "algebra" is a modification of the first half of the title of this work. "Algebra" of al-Khwarizmi is divided into a theoretical part, and a purely practical one, which is devoted to the application of algebraic methods to solving various household, commercial and legal problems. These problems constitute a very significant section of medieval Eastern algebra.

The first treatise of the mathematical content of O. Khayyam - "Difficulties of arithmetic" - was written by him in his youth. At present, this work has not been found, and its content can be judged from the reference of Khayyam himself, located in another work that has survived to this day. Khayyam says that in his treatise he outlined Indian methods for extracting square and cube roots from integers, provided evidence for the correctness of these methods, and most importantly, for the first time generalized them to roots of arbitrary degrees.

Obviously, he knew the rule for raising a binomial to a power, i.e. binomial theorem. The second treatise Khayyam - "On the proofs of problems in algebra and al-muqabala" - compiled around 1069-1074. This essay summarizes the development of algebra as a "scientific art"; According to Khayyam, its subject is unknown quantities that are in some relationship with known quantities, by which these unknowns can be determined. At the same time, unknowns are understood not only as numbers, but also as continuous, geometric quantities. However, Khayyam, like scientists before him, considers here only positive coefficients and roots of equations. Further, in Khayyam's algebraic treatise, a classification of equations, including cubic ones, is given.

Considering quadratic equations, he explains the methods for solving them using examples, in particular those found in Algebra by al-Khwarizmi. Geometric doctrine of O.Khayyam about cubic equations, according to prof. A.P. Yushkevich, "is the crown of Arabic algebra". Fakhr ad-Din Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn an-Husan al-Karaji, a native of Keredj (Iran), worked in Ray and Isfahan as a vizier at the court of the Buyid sultans. Two algebraic treatises by al-Karaji are known - "Al-Fakhri" and "The Miraculous about Arithmetic" (about 1010).

The greatest mathematician and astronomer of the 13th century, Muhammad ibn Muhammad Abu Jaffar Nasir ad-Din at-Tusi was born in Tus (Khorasan) in 1201. Here he received his primary education. It is known that he worked at the court of Nasir, the head of the Ismaili sect of the Asasins. Among the treatises of Nasir at-Din at-Tusi devoted to mathematics, works on plane and spherical trigonometry were of particular importance. The main work of the scientist is "Treatise on the complete quadripartite". At-Tusi paid much attention to various arithmetic and algebraic questions. He wrote an essay on algebra, in which he considered all kinds of problems related to the division of inheritance. Of the scientist's manuscripts, the "Collection on arithmetic using a blackboard and dust" is among the most valuable. It was found that at-Tusi explains the method of extracting roots of any degree, methods of multiplying integers and extracting roots, rules for working with sexagesimal fractions

Thus, the scientists of Central Asia have made a significant, incomparable contribution to the development of all branches of mathematics. It is especially necessary to note the following sections of mathematics: methods of extracting numbers of any degrees from the quadratic and cubic roots; solution of all kinds of cubic equations in a geometric way; expansion of numbers to decimal real numbers, compilation of exact trigonometric tables; ways of performing actions with sixty-digit and ten-digit fractions, etc. Therefore, in the history of the

development of mathematics, the above theory of interconnection, together with the theory of parallel lines, was the impetus for two major discoveries; the inclusion in mathematics of a new section on variables and the formulation of Euclidean geometry.

Summing up, it is necessary to list the main achievements of the scientists of Central Asia in the 9th-15th centuries in the following form: in arithmetic and combinatorics, they developed a system of sexagesimal calculations; made up the theory of decimal fractions; found ways to extract numbers from the root; determined the application of Newton's formulas for any natural exponents; expanded the concept of real numbers. in algebra, algebra was separated as the main independent subject of mathematics; applied numerical algebra in measuring geometries and compiled a geometric theory by solving cubic equations. in trigonometry formed the basis of flat and spherical trigonometry; completed the complete compilation of trigonometric tables. This article contains the names of individual scientists of Central Asia who have made a great contribution to the development of mathematical science.

School teachers of mathematics should not only know all these discoveries, but also be able to use them in the process of teaching schoolchildren, to acquaint them with the history of mathematics. The use of historical materials in the educational process will be able to: intensify interest in the subject; enrich the cognitive sphere of activity; provide assistance in mathematical culture.